

IUPAC Project 2019-031-1-024
Development of a Standard for FAIR Data
Management of Spectroscopic Data

Ontologies4Chem Workshop
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INTERNATIONAL UNION OF
PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY

PROJECT DETAILS

DEVELOPMENT OF A STANDARD FOR FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT OF SPECTROSCOPIC DATA

Project No.: 2019-031-1-024

Start Date: 18 March 2020

End Date:

Cite: <https://iupac.org/project/2019-031-1-024>

Division Name: [Committee on Publications and Cheminformatics Data Standards](#)

Objective

The objective of this project is to apply FAIR data principles to spectroscopic data in the field of chemistry building on IUPAC's extensive expertise in this area. The project will develop standards for the production and dissemination of digital data objects that contain enough spectral data and metadata that they can be (a) findable through semantic searches on the web, (b) available through standard interfaces, (c) interoperable and transferable between systems, and (d) readable and reusable over time, for both humans and machines.

The IUPAC FAIRData Collection

IUPAC FAIRData Collection

A digital collection organized in concordance with the IUPAC FAIRData Recommendations, with an associated **IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid**.

The IUPAC FAIRData Collection

INSTR →

ELN →

PUB →

- 📁 acs.orglett.0c00571
 - ▼ 📁 FID for Publication
 - ▼ 📁 1c
 - ▼ 📁 13C-NMR
 - > 📁 81
 - ▼ 📁 1H-NMR
 - > 📁 80
 - ▼ 📁 HRMS
 - 📄 68075_mari0099_maxis_pos.pdf
 - 📄 1c.mol
 - ▼ 📁 1d
 - > 📁 13C-NMR
 - > 📁 1H-NMR
 - > 📁 HRMS
 - 📄 1d.mol
 - > 📁 3a
 - > 📁 3b

The IUPAC FAIRData Collection

INSTR →

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- normalized
- domain-/subdomain-specific
- data+metadata objects
- multiple representations
- critical associations
- digitally curated
- validation-enabled

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← **API**

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Associations

One to One and One to Many FAIR Relationships

Spectral Datasets

Structures

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

A digital object that describes the collection's representations in a machine-actionable manner, including their properties and their associations.

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

- 📁 acs.orglett.0c00571
 - 📁 FID for Publication
 - 📁 1c
 - 📁 13C-NMR
 - > 📁 81
 - 📁 1H-NMR
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 - > 📁 1H-NMR
 - > 📁 HRMS
 - 📄 1d.mol
 - > 📁 3a
 - > 📁 3b


```
▼ IFD.findingaid:  
  ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.FAIRSpecFindingAid"  
  typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDFindingAid"  
  id: "acs.joc.0c00770"  
  ▼ version: "IFD 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23;FAIRSpec 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23"  
  created: "2022-06-09T04:11Z"  
  ▼ createdBy: "https://github.com/IUPAC/IUPAC-FAIRSpec/blob/main/src/main/java/  
  ▼ contents:  
    citationCount: 1  
    ▼ collections:  
      ▼ 0:  
        count: 11  
        id: "samples"  
        type: "org.iupac.fairdata.sample.IFDSampleCollection"  
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"  
      ▼ 1:  
        count: 54  
        id: "spectra"  
        type: "org.iupac.fairdata.dataobject.IFDDataObjectCollection"  
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"  
      ▼ 2:  
        count: 11  
        id: "sample-spectra-associations"  
        type: "org.iupac.fairdata.derived.IFDSampleDataAssociationCollection"  
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDAssociationCollection"  
    resourceCount: 1  
  ▼ citations:  
    ▼ 0:  
      ▼ title: "[Total Synthesis of (+)-Pestalofone A and (+)-Iso-A82775C]"  
      authors: "Geon Kim, Taewan Kim, Sunkyu Han"
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

```
▼ IFD.findingaid:  
  ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contr_spec.FAIRSpecFindingAid"  
    typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDFindingAid"  
    id: "acs.orglett.0c00571"  
  ▶ version: "IFD 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04... 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23"  
    created: "2022-06-09T04:14Z"  
  ▶ createdBy: "https://github.com/IUPAC...a 0.0.2-alpha+2022.06.09"  
  ▶ contents: {}  
  ▶ citations: []  
  ▶ resources: []  
  ▶ collectionSet: {}
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

```
▼ IFD.findingaid:
  ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contr_spec.FAIRSpecFindingAid"
  typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDFindingAid"
  id: "acs.orglett.0c00571"
  ▶ version: "IFD 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04._ 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23"
  created: "2022-06-09T04:14Z"
  ▶ createdBy: "https://github.com/IUPAC...a 0.0.2-alpha+2022.06.09"
  ▼ contents:
    citationCount: 1
    ▼ collections:
      ▼ 0:
        count: 30
        id: "samples"
        type: "org.iupac.fairdata.sample.IFDSampleCollection"
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"
      ▼ 1:
        count: 30
        id: "structures"
        ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.struc...IFDStructureCollection"
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"
      ▼ 2:
        count: 114
        id: "spectra"
        ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.datao_IFDDataObjectCollection"
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"
      ▼ 3:
        count: 30
        id: "sample-spectra-associations"
        ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.deriv_taAssociationCollection"
        typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDAssociationCollection"
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

▼ IFD.findingaid:	
▶ type:	"org.iupac.fairdata.contr_spec.FAIRSpecFindingAid"
typeExtends:	"org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDFindingAid"
id:	"acs.orglett.0c00571"
▶ version:	"IFD 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04._ 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23"
created:	"2022-06-09T04:14Z"
▶ createdBy:	"https://github.com/IUPAC...a 0.0.2-alpha+2022.06.09"
▶ contents:	{-}
▶ citations:	[-]
▶ resources:	[-]
▼ collectionSet:	
▶ type:	"org.iupac.fairdata.contr_spec.FAIRSpecCollection"
typeExtends:	"org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollectionSet"
id:	"acs.orglett.0c00571"
▼ properties:	
IFD.property.collectionset.len:	199412912
IFD.property.collectionset.ref:	"acs.orglett.0c00571.IFD.collection.zip"
IFD.property.collectionset.source.data.license.name:	"cc-by-nc-4.0"
IFD.property.collectionset.source.data.license.uri:	"https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0"
IFD.property.collectionset.source.publication.uri:	"https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.0c00571"
▶ items:	[-]

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```
▼ IFD.findingaid:  
  ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.FAIRSpecFindingAid"  
    typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDFindingAid"  
    id: "acs.orglett.0c00571"  
  ▼ version: "IFD 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23;FAIRSpec 0.0.2-alpha+2022.04.23"  
    created: "2022-06-09T04:14Z"  
    ▶ createdBy: "https://github.com/IUPAC...a 0.0.2-alpha+2022.06.09"  
    ▶ contents: {}  
    ▶ citations: []  
    ▶ resources: []  
  ▼ collectionSet:  
    ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.FAIRSpecCollection"  
      typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollectionSet"  
      id: "acs.orglett.0c00571"  
      ▶ properties: {}  
    ▼ items:  
      ▶ 0: {}  
      ▶ 1: {}  
      ▶ 2: {}  
      ▶ 3: {}
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid - properties

▼ collectionSet:	
▼ type:	"org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.FAIRSpecCollection"
typeExtends:	"org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollectionSet"
id:	"acs.orglett.0c00571"
▶ properties:	{-}
▼ items:	
▶ 0:	{-}
▶ 1:	{-}
▼ 2:	
▶ type:	"org.iupac.fairdata.datao_IFDDataObjectCollection"
typeExtends:	"org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"
id:	"spectra"
▼ items:	
▼ 0:	
▼ type:	"org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.nmr.FAIRSpecNMRData"
▼ typeExtends:	"org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.FAIRSpecDataObject;org.iupac.fairdat"
label:	"1c/13C-NMR"
▼ properties:	
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.dim:	"1D"
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.nucl.1:	"13C"
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.nucl.2:	"1H"
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.pulse.prog:	"deptqgssp"
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.temperature.absolute:	298.1525
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.freq.nominal:	600
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.manufacturer.name:	"Bruker"
IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.probe.type:	"Z126545_0016 (CPP BBO 600S3 BB-H&F-D-05 Z)"
resourceID:	"1"
▶ representations:	{-}

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid - representations

```
▼ collectionSet:
  ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.FAIRSpecCollection"
  typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollectionSet"
  id: "acs.orglett.0c00571"
  ▶ properties: {}
  ▼ items:
    ▶ 0: {}
    ▶ 1: {}
    ▼ 2:
      ▶ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.dataobject.IFDDataObjectCollection"
      typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDCollection"
      id: "spectra"
      ▼ items:
        ▼ 0:
          ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.nmr.FAIRSpecNMRData"
          ▼ typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.FAIRSpecDataObject;org.iupac.fairdata.dataobject.IFDDataObject;org.iupac.fai"
          label: "13C/13C-NMR"
          ▶ properties: {}
          resourceID: "1"
          ▼ representations:
            ▼ 0:
              ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.nmr.FAIRSpecNMRDataRepresentation"
              ▼ typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.dataobject.IFDDataObjectRepresentation;org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDDRepresentation"
              ▼ ifdType: "IFD.representation.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.vendor.dataset"
              mediaType: "application/zip"
              len: 1215078
              ▼ ref:
                type: "org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDDReference"
                ▶ originPath: "FID for Publication/1c.z_13C-NMR.zip|13C-NMR/81/"
                ▶ path: "21975525/FID_for_Publica_NMR.zip_13C-NMR_81_.zip"
            ▼ 1:
              ▼ type: "org.iupac.fairdata.contrib.fairspec.dataobject.nmr.FAIRSpecNMRDataRepresentation"
              ▼ typeExtends: "org.iupac.fairdata.dataobject.IFDDataObjectRepresentation;org.iupac.fairdata.core.IFDDRepresentation"
              ▼ ifdType: "IFD.representation.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.spectrum.document"
              mediaType: "application/pdf"
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid - parameters

```
▼ items:  
  ▼ 64:  
    label: "compound 5/Compound 5.mnova copy"  
    ▼ properties:  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.dim: "1D"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.freq.1: 500.132350611  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.nucl.1: "1H"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.pulse.prog: "zgpr"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.solvent: "CDCl3"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.temperature.absolute: 290.5  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.expt.title: "2JR85_p.2.fid"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.freq.nominal: 500  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.manufacturer.name: "Bruker/Mestrelab"  
      IFD.property.dataobject.fairspec.nmr.instr.probe.type: "5 mm PABBO BB-1H/D Z-GRD Z110902/0008"  
    ▼ parameters:  
      Acquired Size: 16384  
      Acquisition Date: "2020-01-04T17:35:00"  
      Acquisition Time: 2.7001331  
      Comment: "2JR85 p1"  
      Digital Resolution: "0.0925897394569177"  
      Instrument: "spect"  
      Lowest Frequency: -695.082900560629  
      Modification Date: "2020-01-04T17:35:44"  
      Number of Scans: 64  
      Origin: "Bruker BioSpin GmbH"  
      Presaturation Frequency: "4.67680460663715"  
      Pulse Width: 20  
      Purity: 99.7311604715766  
      Receiver Gain: 203  
      Relaxation Delay: 2  
      Spectral Size: 65536
```

The IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid

- Describes an *IUPAC FAIRData Collection* (which can be fully distributed)
- Discipline-specific
- Highly structured “collection of collections”
- Extendable (as, for example, an *IUPAC FAIRSpec Collection*)
- Class-based object-oriented description

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- “items” may have “properties” that have specific types and ranges of values
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- Generally applicable to any domain, not just chemistry

The IUPAC FAIRData Collection

In Summary

We hope that others with other expertise and perspectives will join us in this endeavor to complete the puzzle and revolutionize the world of chemistry.

Open questions relating to this discussion

- How to best integrate into the IUPAC FAIRData Finding Aid aspects of standard ontologies?
- What should we recommend for serializations of the Finding Aid?
- Will ontologies work for systems that are open and as flexible as ours is?

IUPAC Project 2019-031-1-024
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GitHub: <https://github.com/IUPAC/IUPAC-FAIRSpec>

Principles: [ChemRxiv](#) or [PAC](#)

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